

A comparative study on in-vitro bioactivity of nano-Bioglass synthesized using rice husk and TEOS silica sources

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Bioactive glasses bond to living tissues and, for this reason, they have been studied for their use in different clinical applications, mainly in the field of bone repair and replacement: filling of osseous cavities, manufacturing of small parts of middle ear bone replacement, maxillofacial reconstruction and dental applications. Different bioactive glass and glass ceramics have been synthesized in order to get desired mechanical, chemical properties by obtaining required microstructure. Some of the common components used are Na₂O, CaO, P₂O₅, SiO₂ for synthesis of a unique highly compatible 45S5 Bioglass system. In general, Bioglass has shown higher compatibility when synthesized by sol-gel route compared to melt casting method. Various in-vitro studies have shown that the nucleation and crystallization rates of hydroxycarbonate apatite (HCA) depends on many factors including the sol-gel glass composition.

In the present work, in order to reduce the cost of Bioglass and also enhance the bioactivity of Bioglass a study has been done to synthesize Bioglass from rice husk and TEOS as silica sources. Sintering and crystallization phenomena in powders of a typical bioactive glass composition (45S5 Bioglass) have been investigated in order to gain further understanding of the processes involved in the fabrication of Bioglass based glass-ceramic scaffolds for tissue engineering applications. To assess the in vitro performance and bioreactivity of Bioglass-derived glass-ceramic scaffolds, the biodegradation of samples in simulated body fluid (SBF) was investigated using various techniques, including SEM, XRD and EDX.

Keywords: Bioglass, Rice Husk, Bioactivity